

To: Zach Ducheneaux, Administrator, Farm Service Agency, Department of Agriculture; Sean Torpey Senior Advisor for Policy and Administration, Bureau of Reclamation; Sethuraman Panchanathan, National Science Foundation

From: Elisabeth Ervin-Blankenheim, Ph.D.

Topic: Climate change adaptation: Preservation of healthy soil as related to food security

Executive Summary. The source and sustainability of the food supply begins with soil. Soil degradation from global warming and climate change includes the impact of droughts and desertification, along with rising temperatures and floods. The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act (IIJA), and the CHIPS and Science Act (CHIPS) offer a unique opportunity to address climate mitigation strategies to enhance soil quality and secure the food supply. Policymakers from the Department of Agriculture (USDA), Bureau of Reclamation (USBR), and the National Science Foundation (NSF) should form an overarching Commission for Coordination of Future Food Security (CCFFS) with a clearinghouse for progress and best practices for soil preservation. The CCFFS will enable interagency cooperation to maximize efforts to secure a future with healthy soil and provide ample food by innovation, research, and science-based decision-making.

Issue and Importance. To meet the USDA policy, 2023, for U.S. food security, “access by all people at all times to enough food for an active, healthy life,” requires healthy soil.

- Degradation of soil is directly related to food insecurity, per the United Nations, by lessening crop yield and productivity.
- The U.S. Geological Survey estimates 40% of the land in the U.S. is arid to subarid and at risk of desertification.
- Soil health and crop production are subject to reliable irrigation water sources in semi-arid and arid regions, with the U.S. food supply dependent on crops grown with irrigation water.
- Soil serves as a vital reservoir for carbon sequestration through plant photosynthesis, a critical part of the carbon cycle.

Proposed Policy and Bottom-Line Guidance. The IRA, IIJA, and CHIPS are essential in protecting soil resources. Coordination among agencies is needed to maximize the reach of the initiatives and funds for food security by increasing efforts to keep soils productive and reduce soil degradation from climate impacts.

- The USDA addresses greenhouse gas reduction and carbon sequestration projects through the IRA, which offers an opportunity to consider the role of soil degradation from climate change in food supply and food security.
 - IRA funds of \$3 billion are available for agricultural producers nationwide to participate in voluntary conservation programs and adopt climate-smart practices in fiscal year 2024.
- The USBR oversees the Western Water Infrastructure Plan with IIJA funds for drought contingency plans and irrigation concerns.
- The NSF is tasked, under the CHIPS Act of 2022, to “support research that will lead to innovative solutions to critical food-energy-water system problems.”
 - The food-energy-water nexus situates food production by preserving soil in a broader context with critical interlinkages and feedback between the parts of the system. Research in this area provides an integrated view to formulate recommendations on the best ways to protect soil.
- According to USDA researchers, the health of the nation’s soil is often neglected in policy decisions.
- Business and industry leaders such as Deloitte view the three new federal acts as powerfully transformative, but their success will depend on how they are executed.

Technical and Policy Aspects. The benefits of interagency coordination are cost savings, increased efficiencies, reduced duplication of effort, and better outcomes. Among the challenges are potential bureaucratic complexities, commitment to the process, interagency cooperation, timing in administering and coordinating the new acts, and the technical and operational architecture specific to each agency. Empirical evidence from systems integration and government interoperability studies shows that while the first year can be challenging, subsequent years show improvement in coordination; formation of the CCFFS should begin as soon as possible.